

ENHANCING CRITICAL THINKING IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNERS**Toshtemirova Khosiyat Eshmamat qizi.**

Student of Termiz state university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6639528>

Abstract. *Critical thinking refers to the individuals' ability to think and make correct decisions independently. Nowadays enhancing critical thinking in learners is considered one of the foreign language teachers' tasks due to its high position in foreign language classrooms. There are various factors affecting language learners' critical thinking skills. Among these factors is the assessment methods used. Therefore, through managing the ways of assessing language learners' ability language teachers can help them develop critical thinking skills. In this presentation, some suggestions for language teachers to make sound choice of assessment methods and activities will be presented.*

Keywords: *Assessment, language learners, methods, critical thinking, judgement, independently*

**РАЗВИТИЕ КРИТИЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ У УЧАЩИХСЯ
ИЗУЧАЮЩИХ ИНОСТРАННЫЙ ЯЗЫК**

Аннотация. *Критическое мышление относится к способности людей мыслить и принимать правильные решения самостоятельно. В настоящее время развитие критического мышления у учащихся считается одной из задач преподавателей иностранного языка в связи с его высоким положением на занятиях по иностранному языку. Существуют различные факторы, влияющие на навыки критического мышления изучающих язык. К числу этих факторов относятся используемые методы оценки. Таким образом, управляя способами оценки способностей изучающих язык, учителя могут помочь им развить навыки критического мышления. В этой презентации будут представлены некоторые предложения учителям иностранных языков по правильному выбору методов оценивания и мероприятий.*

Ключевые слова: *оценивание, изучающие язык, методы, критическое мышление, суждения, самостоятельность.*

INTRODUCTION

Critical thinking has been recently introduced and gained a high position in foreign language teaching (FLT) settings so that nowadays enhancing critical thinking in learners is considered one of the foreign language teachers' tasks. Many different factors can affect learners' critical thinking skills. The types of assessment used in the classroom as well as at the end of the course are among these factors. This paper argues that through managing ways of assessment, language teachers can help learners develop critical thinking skills.

2. Critical thinking

Many different definitions have been proposed for critical thinking by various educators such as Lipman (1991); Norris and Ennis (1989); and Siegel (1988). However, there is not much difference among these definitions. As Elder and Paul (1994) state, critical thinking refers to the ability of individuals to take charge of their own thinking and develop appropriate criteria and standards for analyzing their own thinking. Moreover, as Maiorana (1992) maintains, critical

thinking aims at achieving understanding, and evaluating different perspectives, and solving problems.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The promotion of critical thinking into the FLT classrooms is of high significance for several reasons. Firstly, if language learners can take charge of their own thinking, they can monitor and evaluate their own ways of learning more successfully. Second, critical thinking expands the learning experience of the learners and makes the language more meaningful for them. Thirdly, critical thinking has a high degree of correlation with the learners' achievements (Rafi, n.d.). Different studies have confirmed the role of critical thinking in improving ESL writing ability (Rafi, n.d.); language proficiency (Liaw, 2007); and oral communication ability (Kusaka & Robertson, n.d.). The learners may become proficient language users if they have motivation and are taught the ways of displaying critical thinking in foreign language usage, which signifies that the learners must have reflection on their production of ideas, and they may critically support those ideas with logical details (Rafi, n.d.). Language development and thinking are closely related and the teaching of higher-order thinking skills should be an integral part of an L2 curriculum. Educators have emphasized the importance of developing higher-order thinking skills in foreign language classrooms (Chamot, 1995; Tarvin & Al-Arishi, 1991) and empirical evidence supports the effectiveness of teaching critical thinking skills along with the foreign language (Chapple & Curtis, 2000; Davidson, 1994, 1995). In fact, language learners who have developed critical thinking skills are capable of doing activities of which other students may not be capable. Implied in the study by Mahyuddin et al (2004) is that language learners with critical thinking ability are capable of thinking critically and creatively in order to achieve the goals of the curriculum; capable of making decisions and solving problems; capable of using their thinking skills, and of understanding language or its contents; capable of treating thinking skills as lifelong learning; and finally intellectually, physically, emotionally and spiritually well-balanced. However, in spite of the fact that there is little argument among theorists and educators about the importance of thinking skills in language development, in typical school settings, language learning and thinking skills are often treated as independent processes (Miraman & Tishman, 1988; Suhor, 1984). In other words, as Pica (2000) states, in the tradition of English language teaching methodology, the integration of language and thinking skills has been peripheral. It is argued (e.g. Kabilan, 2000) that even communicative language teaching, which emphasizes the use of language as a communication tool, does not really help students to become proficient in the target language. He suggests that for learners to be proficient in a language, they need to be able to think creatively and critically when using the target language. So, it is implied that even communicative approaches to language teaching do not develop critical thinking among learners. Due to the advantages mentioned for enhancing critical thinking in language learners and also little practice in this regards in FLT settings, as Brown (2004) asserts, in an ideal academic language program, the objectives of the curriculum should go beyond linguistic factors to develop critical thinking among learners. In fact, the effectiveness of language teaching will depend upon what is being taught, in addition to language, which learners can consider as a purposeful and relevant extension of their horizons (Widdowson, 1990). Language teachers are among practitioners who can greatly influence the type of learning by language learners. Therefore, one of their responsibilities is to help learners develop critical

thinking abilities. Maybe even more than L1 teachers, L2 teachers have reasons to introduce their students to aspects of critical thinking (Davidson, 1998). As Lipman (2003) says, teachers are responsible for promoting critical thinking in the learners other than helping them to go from one educational level to the next. The responsibility of foreign language teachers is to help their learners acquire critical thinking skills while learning the language. As Mahyuddin et al (2004) assert there is plenty of room for improvement in incorporating the thinking skills into our curricula.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

There is no doubt that the way of assessment in foreign language classrooms highly influences what and how the learners learn. This influence of testing on teaching and learning is referred as washback effect. Alderson and Wall (1993, p. 115) state that “tests are held to be powerful determiners of what happens in the classroom.” In his trichotomy of backwash model, Hughes’s (1993) describes test effects in terms of “participants” such as teachers, students, administrators, materials writers, and publishers, “process” referring to those actions taken by participants to complete teaching and learning tasks and “product” referring to learning outcomes and the quality of learning. Hughes’ model implies that the quality of a test determines to a high degree the level an amount of washback (Pan, 2009).

CONCLUSIONS

Critical thinking needs to be enhanced among language learners due to its significance in developing effective language learning. So promoting critical thinking skills is considered one of the tasks’ of language teachers. They can do this task through various ways, including using appropriate ways of assessment as assessment practices usually determine the learning objectives of the language learners.

References

1. Alderson, C., & Wall, D. (1993). Does washback exist? *Applied Linguistics*, 14, 115-129.
2. Brinton, D. M., Snow, M. A., & Wesche, M. B. (1989). *Content-based second language instruction*. Boston, Massachusetts: Heinle & Heinle.
3. Brown, H.D. (2004) Some practical thoughts about students- sensitive critical pedagogy. *The Language Teacher*, 28(7), 23-27.
4. Bruss, N. and Macedo, D. P. (1985) Toward pedagogy of the question: Conversations with Paulo Freire. *Journal of Education*, 167(2), 7-21.
5. Chamot, A. (1995). Creating a community of thinkers in the ESL/EFL classroom. *TESOL Matters*, 5(5), 1-16.
6. Chapple, L., & Curtis, A. (2000). Content-based instruction in Hong Kong: Student responses to film. *System*, 28, 419-433.
7. Davidson, B. (1994). Critical thinking: A perspective and prescriptions for language teachers. *L The Language Teacher*, 18(4), 20-26.
8. Davidson, B. (1995). Critical thinking education faces the challenge of Japan. *Inquiry: Critical Thinking Across the Disciplines*, 14(3), 41-53.
9. Davidson, B. (1998). A case for critical thinking in the English language classroom. *TESOL Quarterly*, 32, 119-123.
10. Elder, L. & Paul, R. (1994) Critical thinking: Why we must transform our teaching. *Journal of Developmental Education*, 18(1), 34-35.

11. Freire, P. (1970). *Pedagogy of the oppressed*. New York: The Seabury Press.
12. Freire, P. 1973. *Education for critical consciousness*. New York: The Seabury Press.
13. Hughes, A. (1993). *Backwash and TOEFL 2000*. Unpublished manuscript, University of Reading, England.
14. Kabilan, K.M. (2000) Creative and critical thinking in language classroom. *Internet TESL Journal*, 6/6.
15. <http://iteslj.org/Techniques/Kabilan-CriticalThinking.html>